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LEARNERS' SCIENTIFIC LITERACY SKILL: A NECESSITY IN THE SCIENCE EDUCATION

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Teaching and learning processes in the new normal is quite more challenging and need more efforts because it greatly affect the learning outcomes of the learners since there are lots of changes happened in the Philippine educational system. Teachers used their expertise to plan and execute different teaching techniques and strategies to help learners equip their skills, knowledge, and abilities despite of the pandemic. Different distance learning modalities were implemented during the COVID-19 lockdown like modular, online classes, and blended learning modalities as new mode of learning. With these types of teaching and learning modalities, learners' scientific literacy skills and academic performance are quite questionable if the learners really learned.

Skills are one of the most meaningful learnings a 21st century learner should have achieved, because the quality of education primarily is contingent on the learned skills and abilities of the learners. Scientific literacy skill is one of the skills required in the golden era teaching and learning. It is the skill in understanding of the scientific ideas and processes for personal decision-making, involvement in the community and cultural relationships, economic competence, and application of learnings in real-life situations. Scientific literacy skill plays crucial role in our modern society since there are many issues related to science and technology.

Philippines is one of the countries participated in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) of the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) in 2018. In the PISA 2018, Filipino learners scored an average of 357 points in Science Literacy, which is significantly lower than the OECD average of 489 points (OECD, 2019). This result showed that the scientific literacy skill of the Filipino learners is far lower than the OECD average score and has not yet reached the OECD standard. In 2022, the Department of Education - Region III issued Regional Memorandum number 504, s. 2022 about the guidelines on the conduct of the 2022 Regional Diagnostic Assessment (RDA) in all learning areas from Grades 1-10 and core learning areas in Grades 11-12. The results of the RDA in the Division of Nueva Ecija showed that Junior

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High School learners' scientific literacy skill is somehow low due to the low percentage of Minimum Proficiency Level (MPL) of the learners in Science.

The results of the scientific literacy skills of the learners from the different assessments conducted are very alarming and reflect the urgency of improving the quality of education in the Philippines since scientific literacy skills play important role on learner's lifelong learning. These also may become opportunities for teachers to innovate and improve teaching strategies and assessment tools to enhance learners' scientific literacy skills and performance in Science. This time, teachers may utilize appropriate assessment tool relevant to scientific literacy skills and ensure authentic learning. As stated by Cordon, et, al. (2020) learners' Science literacy is important in the development of education. Effective and efficient Science educators are the ones who are able to improve learners' skills in finding answers to questions about materials and phenomena in the environment, and those who teach learners to become knowledgeable decision-makers.

To overcome the challenges of the twenty first century learners in terms of scientific literacy skills, learners need to be equipped with the 21st century skills to ensure their competitiveness in the globalization era. They are expected to be inculcated with the 21st century skills apart of just being performing academically excellent.

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